

Glucose and oxygen as catalysts for “proto-respiration”

One thing glucose is really good at is reacting with hydroxyl radicals. These form from hydroxide ions stored in protoplasm gel, hydrated potassium hydroxide. Glucose and oxygen may be catalysts for proto-respiration, tipping water-oxygen redox balance in favour of degradation of water. In that case, glucose and oxygen has a role in the anode reaction equivalent to zinc in an alkaline battery.

The anode reaction,

Glucose, $(\text{CH}_2\text{O})_6$, catalyses the release of 6 electrons, and the oxygen, 6O_2 , another 6 electrons.

Steps in anode reaction,

The missing O_2 in the reaction comes in at the cathode,

Overall reaction:

Steps in overall reaction:

“Proto-respiration” as a catalyst for photosynthesis

In photosynthesis the process is reversed. Cellular respiration is a catalyst for proto-respiration, and proto-respiration is a catalyst for photosynthesis.

Anode in photosynthesis:

Cathode:

Steps in cathode reaction:

Overall reaction:

Steps in overall reaction:

